

USAGE OF INTERACTIVE GAMES IN TEACHING LANGUAGE AS A SECOND LANGUAGE.

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Abstract: The article deals with interactive language learning games, all useful ways to improve L2 language. Learning is important in teaching.

Аннотация: В статье рассматриваются интерактивные игры для изучения языка, все полезные способы улучшить язык L2. Изучение важно в обучении.

Key words: Quotation efforts, action, Games, statements, pedagogical value, interest or surprise.

Ключевые слова: Цитатные усилия, действие, Игры, высказывания, педагогическая ценность, заинтересованность или удивление.

Language learning is hard work Effort is required at every moment and must be maintained over a long period of time. Games help and encourage many learners to sustain their interest and work.'

The above quote is taken from the introduction to Andrew Wright, David Betteridge and Michael Buckby's 1984 work, 'Games for Language Learning.' While many teachers will wholeheartedly agree with the first sentence, there are those who consider the second to be something of an exercise in indulgence, both for the teacher and the language learner. With this in mind, some never consider actively employing games in their teaching. Indeed, the following statements will infringe on the teaching ethos of quite a few in our profession: Games... help the teacher to create contexts in which the language is useful and meaningful. The learners want to take part and in order to do so must understand what others are saying or have written, and they must speak or write in order to express their own point of view or give information.'

'The need for meaningfulness in language learning has been accepted for some years. A useful interpretation of 'meaningfulness' is that the learners respond to the content in a definite way. If they are amused, angered, intrigued or surprised the content is clearly meaningful to them. Thus the meaning of the language they listen to, read, speak and write will be more vividly experienced and, therefore, better remembered.

If it is accepted that games can provide intense and meaningful practice of language, then they must be regarded as central to a teacher's repertoire. They are thus not for use solely on wet days and at the end of term!' Main body

Games help the teacher to create contexts in which the language is useful and meaningful. Even though games are often associated with fun, we should not lose sight of their pedagogical value, particularly in foreign language teaching and learning. Games are effective as they create motivation, lower students' stress, and give language learners the opportunity for real communication.

According to J. Haldfield, "a game is an activity with rules, a goal and an element of fun.... Games should be regarded as an integral part of the language syllabus". This definition highly evaluates the importance of games in teaching. It shows that games serve not only as an 'amusing activity', but also as a technique to carry out many pedagogical tasks. Classifying games into categories can be difficult because categories often overlap. J.Hadfield proposes two ways of classifying language games. First, language games are divided into two types: linguistic and communicative games. Linguistic games focus on accuracy, such as supplying the correct antonym.

Communicative games presuppose successful exchange of information and ideas. J. Hadfield also offers to classify language games into many more categories: sorting, ordering, or arranging, information gap games, guessing, search games, matching games, labeling, exchanging games; board, role play games. According to W. Lee games can be classified into ten categories: structure games which provide experience of the use of particular patterns of syntax in communication; vocabulary games in which the learners' attention is focused mainly on words; spelling, pronunciation games; number games; listen-and-do games; games and writing; miming and role play; discussion games. Let's discuss some of the common advantages of using games in foreign language teaching and learning. Games promote learners' interaction. Interaction comprises the nature of classroom pedagogy and classroom behavior. Pair or group work is one of the main ways to increase cooperation.

Many games can be played in pairs or in small groups, thereby providing an opportunity to develop their interpersonal skills such as the skill of disagreeing politely or the skill of asking for help. In the classroom learners will definitely participate in the activities. Therefore, in groups or in pairs, they are more willing to ask questions, communicate and discuss topics with their partners and think creatively about how to use foreign language to achieve their goals. The competition in the games gives students a natural opportunity to work together and communicate with each other a lot.

Games improve learners' language acquisition. Thanks to the motivation and interaction created by games, students can acquire knowledge faster and more

effectively than by other means. Games can stimulate and encourage students to participate in the activity since they naturally want to win. Apart from having fun, students are learning. They acquire a new language. Students begin to realize that they have to use the language if they want others to understand what they are saying.

Furthermore, games can lower anxiety. In the easy, relaxed atmosphere which is created by using games, students remember things faster and better. The meaning of the language students listen to, read, speak and write in will be more vividly experienced in a game and, therefore, they will better remember the language they learn. Games increase learners' achievement. Games can involve all the basic language skills, i.e., listening, speaking, reading, and writing, and a number of skills are often involved in the same game.

Games can motivate learners, promote learners' interaction, and improve learners' acquisition. As a result, games can increase learners' achievement, which means that learners' test results, ability of communication, knowledge of vocabulary, or other language skills can improve.

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